

Differences in interfacial damage between single-, double-, and multi-fibre composites, unravelled via *in situ* holotomography

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The interface as the third constituent

Interface

Controls load transfer efficiency

Challenging to characterise reliably

Very small characteristic length

Interface properties

Needed for failure models

Single-fibre test methods

Sensitivity to geometry, absence of neighbouring fibres

The lack of consensus

Values for interfacial properties - Input for numerical models

Pandey et al., 2012

Bruker

Kim et al., 2002

Pitkethly et al., 1993

Methodology

Synchrotron tomography

ID16B, ESRF

- *In situ* capabilities
- Scans at different load steps
- Voxel size: 150 nm
- Acquisition time: < 20 sec

Digital Volume Correlation (DVC)

Digital Image Correlation – Surface

Digital Volume Correlation – Volume

- Intercorrelation of gray levels
- Spatial resolution \rightarrow Strain resolution

Undeformed

Deformed

\rightarrow
DVC

Strain Field

Mehdikhani et al., 2021

DVC prerequisites

The need for heterogeneity

Intrinsic, stable, random speckle pattern

- Absent in conventional polymers
- Insufficient in typical composites

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Material representativeness of a polymer matrix doped with nanoparticles as the random speckle pattern for digital volume correlation of fibre-reinforced composites

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Ensuring representativeness

Fibre breakage

Fibre breaks visible in both fibres

Glass fibre

Interfacial debonding

First observation of longitudinal debonding in 3D

Visible in both fibres

Asymmetric along the fibre cross-section

Matrix cracking

Extensive for glass fibre

Absent for carbon fibre

Double-fibre composites

Two embedded carbon fibres

Similar response as for the carbon single-fibre case

Extensive interfacial debonding

27% UTS

69% UTS

90% UTS

99% UTS

Multi-fibre composites

Absence of debonding

Negligible matrix cracking around fibre breaks

92% UTS

90% UTS

Possible reasons for the discrepancy

1. Matrix size effect
2. Interphase or matrix in situ effect
3. Strain energy release

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Questioning the Representativeness of Damage Mechanisms in Single-Fiber Composites via In Situ Synchrotron X-Ray Holo-Tomography

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Hobbiebrunken et al., 2007

Herrmann et al., 2022

Conclusions

- The representativeness of single-fibre composites warrants further investigation.
- Advanced 3D nano-imaging techniques, such as synchrotron holo-tomography can effectively scrutinise interfacial damage response.

Ongoing research and future work

Thank you for your attention

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